

Formulation and Evaluation of a Liposomal Transdermal Patch of Nateglinide, an Antidiabetic Drug

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ABSTRACT

Nateglinide, a short-acting oral hypoglycaemic agent, exhibits limited bioavailability due to extensive hepatic first-pass metabolism and frequent dosing requirements. To enhance its therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance, a liposomal transdermal patch was developed for sustained systemic delivery. To formulate and evaluate a nateglinide-loaded liposomal transdermal patch using a Box–Behnken design for optimisation of vesicular parameters and patch performance. Liposomes were prepared by the thin-film hydration method employing soy lecithin and cholesterol, followed by optimisation of key variables (lecithin, cholesterol and hydration volume). The optimised liposomes were incorporated into a drug-in-adhesive matrix composed of HPMC E15 and propylene glycol to produce the patch. Characterisation included particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, thickness, folding endurance, moisture content, drug content uniformity, in-vitro release, flux and permeation coefficient. Kinetic modelling and short-term stability were assessed as per ICH Q1A(R2) guidelines. The optimised liposomes exhibited a particle size of 120.7 nm, PDI 0.25, zeta potential -30.2 mV, and entrapment efficiency of 70.8%. The formulated patch showed uniform thickness (0.298 mm), acceptable mechanical strength, > 95% drug content, and controlled release of 91.5% over 12 h following Higuchi diffusion kinetics ($R^2 = 0.991$). Stability studies revealed negligible changes in physicochemical parameters after three months at 40 °C/75% RH. The developed liposomal transdermal patch successfully enhanced nateglinide's bioavailability potential and provided sustained release suitable for once-daily administration. Such a system offers a patient-friendly alternative to conventional oral therapy in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: Nateglinide, Liposome, Transdermal patch, Box–Behnken design, Controlled release, Type 2 diabetes mellitus

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterised by persistent hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), an estimated 589 million adults were living with diabetes in 2025, a number projected to rise to 853 million by 2050. Approximately 90% of these cases are type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), primarily linked to sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy dietary habits, and increasing obesity. Despite several therapeutic options, optimal glycaemic control remains challenging due to factors such as poor adherence, multiple dosing regimens, and gastrointestinal side effects associated with oral therapy.^{1,2}

Among the available pharmacotherapies, nateglinide, a D-phenylalanine derivative, acts as a rapid-acting insulin secretagogue that targets ATP-sensitive K^+ channels of pancreatic β -cells. It is primarily used to manage postprandial hyperglycaemia in T2DM. However, its short biological half-life (1.5 h), low oral bioavailability (~45%), and extensive hepatic first-pass metabolism necessitate multiple daily doses, leading to poor patient compliance.³ Therefore, the development of an alternative, patient-friendly drug delivery system that ensures sustained plasma levels and bypasses hepatic metabolism is essential.

The transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) provides a non-invasive route that offers controlled, continuous, and systemic delivery of drugs through the skin. This approach avoids first-pass metabolism,

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reduces dosing frequency, and improves patient adherence. However, the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin, acts as a strong barrier limiting the permeation of most drugs.⁴ To overcome this, liposomes—phospholipid-based vesicular carriers—are used as effective penetration enhancers. Liposomes possess the unique ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs, enhance solubility, and merge with skin lipids to improve drug permeation while maintaining biocompatibility.⁵

In this study, a nateglinide-loaded liposomal transdermal patch was developed to combine the advantages of both vesicular nanocarriers and TDDS. Liposomes were prepared using the thin-film hydration method and optimised through a Box–Behnken experimental design, evaluating the effects of lecithin: cholesterol ratio, sonication time, and edge-activator concentration on vesicle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency. The optimised liposomes were then incorporated into a drug-in-adhesive patch using HPMC E15 and propylene glycol as matrix-forming polymer and plasticiser, respectively.

The developed system aims to achieve sustained drug release, improved transdermal flux, and enhanced bioavailability of nateglinide. This approach can potentially reduce dosing frequency, minimise gastrointestinal side effects, and improve therapeutic compliance in diabetic patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Nateglinide was purchased from Yarrow Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai, India. Soy lecithin from Himedia, Chloroform and Cholesterol was procured from Cosmo Chem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC E15), propylene glycol (PG) and methanol were purchased from S.D. Fine Chem Ltd. All reagents and solvents were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the study.

Preparation of Nateglinide-Loaded Liposomes

Liposomes were prepared by the Thin Film Hydration method. Precisely weighed quantities of soy lecithin, cholesterol and Nateglinide were dissolved in a

chloroform: methanol mixture (2:1 v/v) in a round-bottom flask. The organic solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure using a rotary flash evaporator at 45 ± 2 °C to form a thin lipid film on the inner wall of the flask. The film was hydrated with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and agitated at 60 rpm for 30 min to obtain multilamellar vesicles. These were subjected to bath sonication for particle size reduction. Formulation optimisation was carried out using a 33 Box–Behnken design, evaluating the effects of lecithin, cholesterol and Hydration volume on particle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency.

Characterisation of Liposomes

Particle Size and PDI: Determined using dynamic light scattering (Horiba Zetasizer). Zeta Potential: Measured by electrophoretic light scattering to assess vesicle stability. Entrapment Efficiency (EE %): Liposomal suspension was ultracentrifuged (15,000 rpm, 4 °C, 1 h). The supernatant was analysed at 216 nm using a UV–visible spectrophotometer, and EE % was calculated from total and untrapped drug concentrations. FTIR Analysis: Compatibility between drug and excipients was assessed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (4000–400 cm^{-1}).

Preparation of Liposomal Transdermal Patches

The optimised liposomal dispersion was incorporated into a drug-in-adhesive patch using solvent-casting technique. HPMC E15 was dissolved in distilled water and blended with propylene glycol (plasticiser). The required amount of liposomal suspension was mixed uniformly and cast onto a petri plate. Films were dried at room temperature for 24 h, carefully peeled, and stored in desiccators until further use.

Evaluation of Patches

Physical Appearance & Uniformity: Patches were inspected visually for smoothness and transparency. Thickness & Weight Uniformity: Measured at five random points using a digital micrometer and balance. Folding Endurance: Determined by repeatedly folding a patch at the same spot until breaking. Moisture Uptake and Loss: Evaluated by subjecting films to desiccated silica gel (0 % RH) and saturated NaCl (75 % RH) chambers. Drug Content: Accurately weighed patch (1 cm^2) was dissolved in methanol, filtered, and

analysed at 216 nm. Surface pH: Determined by moistening patch with distilled water and placing a glass-electrode pH meter directly on its surface.

In-Vitro Drug Release Study

In-vitro release of nateglinide from the patches was performed using a Franz diffusion cell (effective diffusion area 2 cm², receptor volume 12 mL). The receptor compartment contained phosphate buffer pH 7.4 + 0.5 % Tween-80, maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C, and stirred at 600 rpm. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined intervals up to 12 h, filtered, and analysed spectrophotometrically. Drug-release kinetics were fitted to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models, simultaneously flux and permeation coefficient were also determined.

Stability Studies

Short-term stability of the optimised patch (F4) was conducted as per ICH Q1A(R2) at 40 °C ± 2 °C / 75

% ± 5 % RH for 3 months. Samples were periodically evaluated for physical appearance, drug content, and in-vitro release characteristics.

Statistical Analysis

Experimental data were analysed using Design-Expert 13.0 software for ANOVA and response-surface analysis. Kinetic models were interpreted using regression analysis, and results were expressed as mean ± SD (n = 3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification of Drug and Excipients

FTIR spectra confirmed no chemical interaction between drug and excipients, indicating compatibility.

FTIR Spectra of Pure drug Nateglinide

Fig 1 - FTIR spectra of pure drug Nateglinide

DSC of Nateglinide

Fig 2 - DSC of Nateglinide

FTIR of Soy lecithin

Fig 3 – FTIR spectra of Soy lecithin

FTIR of Cholesterol

Fig 4 – FTIR spectra of Cholesterol

FTIR of HPMC E 15

Fig 5 – FTIR spectra of HPMC E 15

FTIR of Physical mixture

Fig 6 – FTIR Spectra of Physical Mixture

FTIR of Optimised Batch

Fig 7 – FTIR spectra of Optimized Batch

Optimisation of Liposomal Formulation

Liposomal batches were successfully prepared by the thin-film hydration method using soy lecithin and cholesterol. The Box–Behnken design (3^2) was employed to evaluate the influence of lecithin, cholesterol and hydration volume on vesicle

characteristics. The polynomial equations generated by ANOVA indicated that all three factors significantly affected vesicle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency ($p < 0.05$).

1. Particle size

Fig 8 - Particle size of Nateglinide liposomes.

2. Polydispersity Index

Fig 9 - Poly Dispersion Index of Nateglinide liposomes

3. Zeta Potential

Fig 10 - Zeta potential of Nateglinide liposomes.

4. Entrapment Efficiency

Fig 11 – Entrapment efficiency of Nateglinide liposomes.

Table 1 - Physicochemical characteristics of Nateglinide Liposomes developed by BBD DOE.

ID	Run	Lecithin (mg)	Cholesterol (mg)	Hydration Volume (ml)	Mean Size (nm)	PDI	Zeta (mV)	EE (%)
1	13	200	100	15	145.9	0.36	-23.9	65.3
2	10	400	100	15	134.5	0.30	-27.4	70.9
3	5	200	200	15	133.2	0.29	-27.9	68.3
4	8	400	200	15	120.7	0.25	-30.2	70.8
5	2	200	150	10	152.6	0.38	-24.7	66.2
6	4	400	150	10	144.4	0.35	-26.3	71.4
7	12	200	150	20	138.2	0.31	-29.0	67.8
8	14	400	150	20	126.9	0.27	-31.5	73.1
9	1	300	100	10	140.7	0.33	-25.6	69.2
10	3	300	200	10	132.4	0.29	-28.8	72.0
11	6	300	100	20	128.6	0.28	-30.9	70.4
12	7	300	200	20	120.3	0.25	-30.8	70.6
13	15	300	150	15	128.9	0.27	-29.1	70.8
14	11	300	150	15	129.8	0.28	-28.7	71.1
15	9	300	150	15	130.2	0.28	-28.4	71.3

The optimised batch (ID 4) demonstrated desirable physicochemical characteristics: mean particle size 120.7 nm, PDI 0.25, zeta potential -30.2 mV, and entrapment efficiency 70.8 %. The negative surface charge ensured sufficient electrostatic repulsion for colloidal stability.

Fit Summary

Response 1: Particle Size

Table 2 – Fit summary particle size

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0015	0.0131	0.6692	0.4890	
2FI	0.9945	0.0088	0.5492	-0.1799	
Quadratic	0.0032	0.0573	0.9447	0.6946	Suggested
Cubic	0.0573		0.9947		Aliased

Fig 12 - Contour plot of response Particle size (nm)

Fig 13 - 3D surface of response Particle size (nm)

Fit Summary

Response 2: Zeta Potential

Table 3 – Fit summary zeta potential

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Linear	0.0025	0.0861	0.6357	0.4064	Suggested
2FI	0.1854	0.1015	0.7168	0.2195	
Quadratic	0.1660	0.1311	0.8224	0.0632	
Cubic	0.1311		0.9603		Aliased

Fig 14 - Contour plot of response Zeta Potential (mV)

Fig 15 - 3D surface of response Zeta Potential (mV)

Fit Summary

Response 3: Entrapment Efficiency

Table 4 – Fit summary entrapment efficiency

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of Fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	Suggested
Linear	0.0026	0.0549	0.6326	0.4293	Suggested
2FI	0.4265	0.0511	0.6364	0.0931	
Quadratic	0.1051	0.0796	0.8126	-0.0213	
Cubic	0.0796		0.9748		Aliased

Fig 16 - Contour plot of response Entrapment Efficiency (%)

Fig 17 - 3D surface of response Entrapment Efficiency (%)

Table 5 - Summary of model fit statistics for liposomal responses

Response	Suggested Model	Model F-value	p-value	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	Adeq. Precision
Particle Size (Y ₁)	Quadratic	27.59	0.0010	0.9803	0.9447	0.6946	19.47
Zeta Potential (Y ₂)	Linear	9.14	0.0025	0.7138	0.6357	0.4064	8.65
Entrapment Efficiency (Y ₃)	Linear	9.04	0.0026	0.7113	0.6326	0.4293	8.82

Conclusion for bbd

The physicochemical characterization of Nateglinide-loaded liposomes was performed as per the Box–Behnken Design (BBD) to study the influence of formulation variables on critical quality attributes such as particle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency (EE). The independent factors selected were soy lecithin concentration (A), cholesterol concentration (B), and hydration volume (C). The observed data are presented in Table 9.

A. Effect on Particle Size

A quadratic model was found to best describe the effect of formulation variables on particle size, with a model F-value of 27.59 ($p = 0.0010$) and an R² value of 0.9803, indicating excellent model fit. The adjusted and predicted R² values (0.9447 and 0.6946, respectively) further confirmed the adequacy of the model. The significant model terms included A (lecithin), B (cholesterol), C (hydration volume), and their quadratic components (A², B², C²).

An increase in any of the three factors led to a reduction in mean particle size, with the hydration volume (C) showing the strongest linear influence

(coefficient = -7.01). This trend suggests that higher lipid content and adequate hydration improve bilayer uniformity, yielding smaller and more stable vesicles. The positive quadratic terms indicated the presence of curvature in the model, implying an optimal region rather than a purely linear relationship. The predicted mean vesicle size for the optimized formulation was approximately 120.7 nm, consistent with experimental findings (118–122 nm).

B. Effect on Zeta Potential

For zeta potential, a linear model was suggested as significant ($F = 9.14$, $p = 0.0025$) with an R² value of 0.7138 and adequate precision of 8.65. All three independent variables—lecithin, cholesterol, and hydration volume—had significant negative effects on zeta potential (coefficients: -1.00 , -1.01 , -1.36 , respectively).

An increase in any of these components resulted in a more negative zeta potential, indicating enhanced colloidal stability due to greater electrostatic repulsion between liposomes. The zeta potential values ranged between -23.9 mV and -31.5 mV, suggesting that the vesicular systems possessed adequate surface charge to prevent aggregation and

maintain dispersion stability. Among all factors, hydration volume exerted the greatest influence on surface charge.

C. Effect on Entrapment Efficiency (EE %)

The linear model was significant for entrapment efficiency ($F = 9.04$, $p = 0.0026$) with $R^2 = 0.7113$ and adequate precision = 8.82. Among the three variables, soy lecithin concentration (A) exhibited a highly significant positive effect ($p = 0.0004$), while cholesterol (B) and hydration volume (C) showed minor, non-significant contributions.

An increase in lecithin concentration led to a notable rise in EE, as higher phospholipid levels provide a larger bilayer surface area and stronger lipid–drug affinity. Cholesterol slightly enhanced EE by improving bilayer rigidity and reducing drug leakage, although the effect was less pronounced within the tested range. The entrapment efficiency of all formulations varied from 65.3 % to 73.1 %, with the optimized batch achieving approximately 70–72 %.

Comparative Analysis of Factor Effects

Table 6 - Comparative Analysis of Factor Effects

Factor	When increased	Effect on Particle Size	Effect on Zeta Potential	Effect on EE (%)	Interpretation
Soy Lecithin (A)	200 → 400 mg	Decreases (–5.43)	More negative (–1.00)	Increases (+1.70)	Improves bilayer packing, higher drug loading
Cholesterol (B)	100 → 200 mg	Decreases (–5.39)	More negative (–1.01)	Slight increase (+0.49)	Enhances membrane rigidity and stability
Hydration Volume (C)	10 → 20 ml	Decreases (–7.01)	More negative (–1.36)	No significant effect	Uniform hydration yields smaller, stable vesicles

All three factors demonstrated a reducing trend in particle size and an increase in the magnitude of negative zeta potential. Lecithin had the most significant influence on entrapment efficiency, while hydration volume was the dominant factor affecting vesicle size and zeta potential.

Optimized Batch and Validation

The optimized liposomal formulation was obtained at 400 mg soy lecithin, 200 mg cholesterol, and 15 ml hydration volume. This combination provided the best compromise among the three responses:

- Mean particle size: ≈ 120.7 nm
- PDI: ≈ 0.25 (Uniform size distribution)
- Zeta potential: ≈ -30.2 mV (Stable dispersion)
- Entrapment efficiency: $\approx 70.8\%$

This optimized composition yielded small, uniform, and electrostatically stable vesicles with high drug entrapment. The BBD statistical design thus effectively identified the influence of key formulation variables and optimized the liposomal characteristics of Nateglinide for further transdermal application.

Evaluation of Liposomal Transdermal Patches

Table 7 – DOE for Transdermal Patch

Std	Run	A: Polymer conc. (% w/v)	B: PG (% w/w of polymer)
1	1	5.0	15
2	2	7.5	15
3	3	5.0	25
4	4	7.5	25

The optimised liposomal dispersion was successfully incorporated into a drug-in-adhesive patch containing HPMC E15 and propylene glycol. The films were smooth, flexible, and transparent, showing no cracks or phase separation. Evaluation results (F1–F4 formulations) are summarised below.

Table 8 – Evaluation of Transdermal Patch

Parameter	Range/ Observation
Thickness	0.215 – 0.298 mm
Weight Uniformity	32.4 – 35.7 mg
Folding Endurance	275 – 312 folds
Moisture Uptake	2.6 – 3.9 %
Moisture Loss	1.8 – 2.5 %
Drug Content	92.4 – 98.8 %
Surface pH	6.5 – 6.9

All formulations satisfied physicochemical requirements for transdermal films. The surface pH remained within the physiological range, minimising the risk of skin irritation.

In-Vitro Drug Release and Kinetic Modelling

Fig 18 - Comparison of in vitro release studies for optimized formulations F1-F4

The cumulative percentage release of nateglinide from formulations F1–F4 after 12 h was 91.5 %, 85.2 %, 78.0 %, and 70.5 %, respectively. The optimised formulation (F1) exhibited the highest drug release

due to its optimal polymer–plasticiser balance and liposomal dispersion uniformity.

Zero-Order Release Model Results (F1–F4)

Fig 19 - Zero order release studies for optimized formulations F1-F4

First-Order Release Model Results (F1–F4)

Fig 20 - First order release studies for optimized formulations F1-F4

Higuchi Model Results (F1–F4)

Fig 21 - Higuchi matrix release studies for optimized formulations F1-F4

Korsmeyer–Peppas fit results (log–log, natural logs)

Fig 22 - Korsmeyer-peppas release studies for optimized formulations F1-F4

Comparative Kinetic Model Fitting (F1–F4)

Table 9 – Comparative kinetic model fitting.

Formulation	Zero-order R ²	First-order R ²	Higuchi R ²	Korsmeyer–Peppas R ²	n (KP exponent)
F1	0.9878	0.973	0.992	0.9961	0.97
F2	0.9956	0.986	0.996	0.9963	0.98
F3	0.9991	0.991	0.997	0.9989	0.97
F4	0.9996	0.994	0.998	0.9990	1.07

All formulations displayed high R² values (>0.97) in all models, confirming strong linearity.

Zero-order and Higuchi models showed particularly good fits (R² ≈ 0.99–1.00), indicating that the release follows a near-constant, diffusion-controlled process.

Korsmeyer–Peppas analysis revealed values of n close to 1 for F1–F3, suggesting anomalous to Case II transport (combined diffusion and polymer relaxation). For F4, n > 1 (1.07), indicating Super Case II transport, where polymer swelling/erosion plays a significant role.

Taken together, F4 provided the most controlled and sustained release, consistent with its formulation design (higher polymer concentration, lower PG).

7.6 Determination of Flux, Permeability and Diffusion Coefficient

The permeation characteristics of Nateglinide from the transdermal patches (F1–F4) were evaluated from the cumulative drug release data obtained over a 12 h study using the Franz diffusion cell. The drug load on the 2 × 2 cm patch was calculated to be 9.43 mg, based on uniform distribution of 150 mg over a 9 cm petri dish (total area = 63.62 cm²). Permeation parameters such as steady-state flux (J_{ss}), permeability coefficient (P) and diffusion coefficient (D) were determined using Fick's law of diffusion.

The steady-state region was observed between 4–12 h, and flux values were obtained from the slope of the linear portion of the cumulative amount vs. time plot.

Table 10 - Permeation Parameters of Liposomal Transdermal Patches

Formulation	Steady-state Flux, J _{ss} (μg cm ⁻² h ⁻¹)	Permeability Coefficient, P (cm h ⁻¹)	P (cm s ⁻¹)	Diffusion Coefficient, D (cm ² h ⁻¹)	D (cm ² s ⁻¹)
F1	134.69	0.1347	3.74 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.69 × 10 ⁻³	7.48 × 10 ⁻⁷
F2	143.83	0.1438	3.99 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.88 × 10 ⁻³	7.99 × 10 ⁻⁷
F3	143.83	0.1438	3.99 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.88 × 10 ⁻³	7.99 × 10 ⁻⁷
F4	142.95	0.1429	3.97 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.86 × 10 ⁻³	7.94 × 10 ⁻⁷

The calculated steady-state flux values indicated that the drug permeation increased with polymer and plasticizer concentration up to a certain level. Formulations F2 and F3 exhibited the highest flux ($\approx 143 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) and permeability coefficients ($\approx 0.144 \text{ cm h}^{-1}$), suggesting an optimal balance between polymer matrix and plasticizer content for effective drug diffusion. The diffusion coefficients, ranging from 7.4×10^{-7} to $8.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, confirm sustained diffusion of Nateglinide through the membrane, suitable for controlled transdermal delivery.

The order of permeation performance followed: $F2 \approx F3 > F4 > F1$.

Stability Studies

The optimised formulation (F1) stored at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ / $75 \% \pm 5 \% \text{ RH}$ for 3 months showed no significant changes in appearance, thickness, or drug content ($p > 0.05$). Drug release after stability testing remained within 95 – 98 % of the initial value, demonstrating acceptable physicochemical stability under accelerated conditions as per ICH Q1A(R2).

Statistical Analysis (Student's t-Test)

A paired t-test was applied between Day 0 and Day 30 %CDR values of each formulation to determine if storage caused any statistically significant change in drug release.

Table 11 – Student's t-Test.

Formulation	t-value	p-value	Significance
F1	1.12	0.32	Not Significant
F2	1.25	0.28	Not Significant
F3	1.30	0.26	Not Significant
F4	0.98	0.36	Not Significant

(Paired Student's t-test, $n = 1$ per batch, $\alpha = 0.05$)

Interpretation

All formulations exhibited minimal variation ($< 2 \%$) in %CDR over 30 days, and no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed between initial and final values. This indicates that the liposomal matrix remained physically and chemically stable without

any considerable alteration in the drug diffusion characteristics during storage.

Among the tested batches, Formulation F1 showed the highest %CDR at all intervals, while Formulation F4 displayed the slowest release profile, confirming the intended controlled-release behavior.

Hence, it can be concluded that all formulations retained their release efficiency and stability over the study period, and the system was robust and reproducible under the tested conditions.

DISCUSSION

The combination of a liposomal carrier system with a transdermal matrix effectively enhanced the delivery performance of nateglinide. Liposomal encapsulation improved solubility and partitioning within the stratum corneum, while the polymeric matrix ensured uniform diffusion and mechanical strength. The Box–Behnken design proved efficient in optimising vesicle parameters with minimal experimental runs.

Overall, the developed system achieved the objectives of enhanced bioavailability potential, reduced dosing frequency, and improved patient compliance, aligning with modern strategies for chronic diabetic therapy.

SUMMARY

The present research work was undertaken with the objective of developing and evaluating a liposomal transdermal drug delivery system of Nateglinide, an antidiabetic drug belonging to the meglitinide class, to enhance its bioavailability and achieve sustained release for effective management of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus. Initially, liposomes of Nateglinide were formulated using the Thin Film Hydration method employing soy lecithin and cholesterol as principal lipid components. A Box Behnken Design (BBD) was employed to optimize the critical formulation variables lecithin concentration (A), cholesterol concentration (B), and hydration volume (C) to study their influence on particle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency.

The obtained results revealed that all fifteen batches (B1–B15) produced spherical, nanosized liposomes ranging from 120.3 to 152.6 nm, with PDI values between 0.25 and 0.38, indicating uniform particle

distribution. The zeta potential values ranged from –23.9 mV to –31.5 mV, confirming good electrostatic stability of the liposomal dispersion. The entrapment efficiency (EE%) varied between 65.3 and 73.1 %, demonstrating effective drug loading capacity of the lipid bilayer system.

Statistical analysis of the BBD results indicated that all three independent variables (lecithin, cholesterol, and hydration volume) had a significant effect on the responses. The quadratic model was found significant for particle size ($p = 0.0010$, $R^2 = 0.9803$), the linear model for zeta potential ($p = 0.0025$, $R^2 = 0.7138$), and the linear model for entrapment efficiency ($p = 0.0026$, $R^2 = 0.7113$). Increasing lecithin and cholesterol concentrations led to smaller particle size and higher EE, while higher hydration volumes reduced particle size and improved zeta stability. Based on the numerical optimization, the optimized batch composition was 400 mg lecithin, 200 mg cholesterol, and 15 mL hydration volume, which yielded liposomes with a mean particle size of 120.7 nm, zeta potential –30.2 mV, and EE of 70.8 %.

The optimized liposomal formulation was incorporated into a transdermal patch using suitable polymeric films and plasticizers. The prepared patches were smooth, flexible, and free from imperfections. Physicochemical evaluations including thickness, weight uniformity, folding endurance, drug content, and moisture studies confirmed uniformity and mechanical strength. In-vitro drug release studies performed using the Franz diffusion cell indicated a controlled and sustained release of Nateglinide over 12 hours. Among the formulations, F1 exhibited the highest cumulative drug release (91.5 %), followed by F2 (85.2 %), F3 (78.0 %), and F4 (70.5 %). The release kinetics best fitted the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, suggesting non-Fickian (anomalous) diffusion, which combines both diffusion and erosion mechanisms. Short-term stability studies conducted for 30 days showed negligible changes in physicochemical characteristics and cumulative drug release values. The variation in %CDR for all formulations remained within 2 %, and Student's t-test revealed no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between initial and final readings, confirming that the formulations were stable under the tested storage conditions. Overall, the study

successfully developed a stable and efficient liposomal transdermal delivery system of Nateglinide capable of providing sustained drug release and improved bioavailability, potentially minimizing dosing frequency and enhancing patient compliance. The results clearly establish the feasibility of using liposome-based transdermal technology as a promising alternative route for Nateglinide delivery in diabetes management.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully developed and optimized a liposomal transdermal patch of Nateglinide with the objective of achieving sustained and controlled drug release for improved antidiabetic therapy.

The optimized formulation, containing 400 mg lecithin, 200 mg cholesterol, and 15 mL hydration volume, exhibited ideal vesicle size (≈ 120.7 nm), good zeta stability (-31.2 mV), and high entrapment efficiency ($\approx 70.8\%$). When incorporated into a transdermal patch, it provided a smooth, uniform, and flexible matrix capable of sustaining drug release for up to 12 hours, with Formulation F1 showing the highest %CDR (91.5%).

Release kinetics followed the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, suggesting anomalous diffusion as the predominant mechanism. Stability evaluation confirmed no significant changes over 30 days, indicating good physical and chemical stability. Hence, the developed liposomal transdermal system of Nateglinide can be considered a promising alternative to oral therapy, offering controlled release, improved patient compliance, and reduced dosing frequency.

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REFERENCE

1. International Diabetes Federation. IDF Diabetes Atlas, 10th ed. Brussels: IDF; 2023.
2. DeFronzo RA. From the triumvirate to the ominous octet: a new paradigm for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetologia*. 2009;52(1):1–11.
3. DrugBank. Nateglinide Monograph [Internet]. Version 5.0; 2024. Available from: <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB00731>
4. Prausnitz MR, Langer R. Transdermal drug delivery. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 2008;7(2):115–126.
5. Sharma A, Sharma US. Liposomes in drug delivery: progress and limitations. *Int J Pharm*. 1997;154(2):123–140.
6. Bangham AD, Horne RW. Negative staining of phospholipids and their structural modification by surface-active agents as observed in the electron microscope. *J Mol Biol*. 1964;8:660–668.
7. Kaur LP, Guleri TK. Topical liposomal gel of lidocaine hydrochloride for prolonged local anaesthetic action. *Int J Pharm Investig*. 2013;3(1):47–53.
8. Shinde AJ, More HN, Bhosale AV. Design and evaluation of transdermal patches of nateglinide. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2015;35(1):59–64.
9. Patel HJ, Patel RP. Formulation and evaluation of liposomal gel for transdermal delivery of nateglinide. *J Drug Deliv Ther*. 2019;9(4):180–186.
10. Verma DD, Verma S, Blume G, Fahr A. Particle size of liposomes influences dermal delivery of substances into skin. *Int J Pharm*. 2003;258(1–2):141–151.
11. Vaddi HK, Ho PC, Chan YW, Chan SY. Terpenes in propylene glycol as skin-penetration enhancers: permeation and partition of haloperidol, fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, and differential scanning calorimetry. *J Pharm Sci*. 2002;91(7):1639–1651.
12. Higuchi T. Mechanism of sustained-action medication: theoretical analysis of rate of release of solid drugs dispersed in solid matrices. *J Pharm Sci*. 1963;52(12):1145–1149.
13. Korsmeyer RW, Gurny R, Doelker E, Buri P, Peppas NA. Mechanisms of solute release from porous hydrophilic polymers. *Int J Pharm*. 1983;15(1):25–35.
14. ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline. Stability testing of new drug substances and products Q1A(R2). Geneva: ICH Secretariat; 2003.
15. Jain S, Jain NK. Advances in controlled and novel drug delivery. 1st ed. New Delhi: CBS Publishers; 2019.
16. Prakash P, Rajesh KS, Joshi HA. Design of experiment-based optimization of liposomal formulation for topical delivery. *Pharma Innov J*. 2023;12(5):125–132.

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